

CATALYSTS FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF METHANOL AT LOW PRESSURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7791309>

A prerequisite for the industrial implementation of methanol synthesis at low pressures (≈ 5 MPa) is the presence of a catalyst, which should have high activity at relatively low temperatures. It has long been known that copper-containing catalysts are more active than zinc-chromium catalysts. Such copper-containing catalysts were studied in the 1930s for the purpose of industrial synthesis of methanol. In some publications, they are called "Blasyak catalysts".

Many on methanol synthesis over copper-zinc and copper-magnesium catalysts it is impossible not to mention the first scientific works (1928-38). However, this the introduction of catalysts into industrial practice was unsuccessful in those years, because their term of service was short. This was mainly due to the very low stability of catalysts to catalytic poisons (sulfur, chlorine, phosphorus, metal carbonyls), as well as their slight sensitivity to temperature changes.

Zinc-chromium oxide catalysts used in high-pressure synthesis exhibit high stability against sulfur. A concentration of H_2S of 30 ppm or higher in the purified gas used for methanol synthesis is very acceptable. In contrast, the content of catalyst poisons for copper catalysts is limited to 1 ppm based on H_2S . Only with the advent of new processes in gas purification, for example, the Rectisol process, it became possible to reduce the content of sulfur compounds in the synthesis gas to 0.1 ppm, and thus achieve catalyst operation for 3 years or more.

Another reason for the rapid deactivation of copper catalysts is the recrystallization of copper at very high temperatures. Under the conditions of methanol synthesis, the copper in the catalyst is in the metallic state. The Tamman point (that is, the minimum temperature at which the mobility of Cu atoms in the crystal lattice is noticeable) is $\approx 190^\circ C$.

Therefore, the maximum permissible synthesis temperature for copper-containing catalysts is $270^\circ C$. At high temperatures, rapid deactivation of catalysts occurs due to recrystallization of copper. The first successful attempt to use copper-containing catalysts in the industrial synthesis of methanol was made at a chemical plant in Oswiecim, Republic of Poland.

The prepared catalyst had the following composition: 62.5% CuO , 25% ZnO , 7.5% Al_2O_3 and 5.0% H_2O . Catalyst Dautherm A coolant (an azeotropic and eutectic mixture of 73% diphenyl oxide and 27% diphenyl). operated at relatively high temperature and pressure ($220-300^\circ C$ and 15-25MPa) in a cooled tubular reactor. No recirculation was used for the exhaust gas: a mixture of synthesis gas and converted natural gas was sent directly to the catalyst. Under these conditions, the productivity of the catalyst was 1.25 tons of methanol per 1 m^3 of catalyst per hour. At a sulfur content of 1-2 mg/m^3 in synthesis gas, the lifetime of the catalyst was only 3-5 months. Based on thermodynamic and kinetic data, copper-containing catalysts, in contrast to zinc-chromium catalysts, in the presence of 4.5-5.5% (volume) CO_2 and $H_2:CO$ synthesis gas ratio of approximately $\approx 3.5:1$ provides optimal performance.

After 1959, a new era began in the development of copper-containing catalysts, which culminated in the industrial and economically efficient synthesis of methanol at low pressure and temperature. Copper-containing catalysts developed in Frankfurt have been successfully used in the industrial synthesis of methanol at low pressure.

The optimal catalyst is obtained not only by changing the composition, but the preparation method can be decisive. In general, copper-containing catalysts are prepared by co-precipitation of the components from more or less dilute salt solutions.

It is very important to maintain the right temperature and pH during an emergency. After the filter cake is dried and sieved, the resulting catalyst mass is turned into tablets of the required size. Before starting, the catalyst must be reduced, which means that the copper oxide must be converted to the catalytically active metal form. Since the reduction of CuO occurs with a large heat release, in order to maintain the maximum activity of the catalyst, it should not be allowed to overheat, and it should be reduced in a stream of inert gas at a lower concentration of hydrogen. After this careful return, the catalyst is transferred to the "formation" stage.

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